

Procalcitonin: Practicing Antibiotic Stewardship in Pediatric Critical Care

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Background

- Antibiotic overuse is prominent in pediatrics and can lead to antimicrobial resistance, increased mortality rate, adverse events, drug toxicity, *Clostridium Difficile* infections and additional financial costs
- Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs), such as bacterial tracheitis, are a major cause of pediatric mortality. Majority of patients with tracheitis are admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU)
- Standard antibiotic treatment is 7-10 days
- Procalcitonin (PCT) is a reliable biomarker for diagnosis of bacterial infections. PCT levels of <0.25 ng/mL have 94% sensitivity in identifying the absence of bacteria
- Literature has shown that PCT-guided care resulted in 2 to 3-day reduction in total antibiotic days in LRTIs

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Quality Improvement (QI) project was to apply a PCT-driven algorithm to decrease the length of antibiotic treatment for bacterial tracheitis from 7 to 5 days, without demonstrating adverse outcomes

Methods

Design: QI project guided by the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model with retrospective data collection

Setting: A 30-bed pediatric ICU at a Children's Hospital in Southern California

Sample: 15 pediatric patients diagnosed with bacterial tracheitis between the ages of 1 month and 18 years

Measures: Length of days on antibiotics, length of stay (LOS), days in the ICU, readmissions

Framework: PDSA Model for Quality Improvement

Results

Procalcitonin Algorithm (PROCa™)

Limitations

- Single pediatric center with a focus only on ICU
- Limited sample size with short project duration
- Challenging to provide formal training for rotating residents placing orders
- Providers still learning how to interpret PCT results given novelty of biomarker

Discussion

- 15 tracheitis patients met the inclusion & exclusion criteria during the 3-month pilot
- Algorithm fully implemented 30% of the time and partially 47% of the time
- When PROCa™ was fully implemented, patients with uncomplicated tracheitis required ≤ 5 days of IV antibiotics with no readmissions
- Application of PROCa™ successfully decreased LOS & ICU days in 47% of patients
- 463 levels measured during the first 8 months PCT offered in-house

Recommendations

- Ongoing education and training to prevent disengagement and non-adherence
- Electronic alerts to remind providers to initiate the protocol
- Adding PCT lab to the *Tracheitis Order Set* to streamline process
- "Tracheitis Pathway" sign on room door to identify which patient is on PROCa™

Conclusion

- PCT helps support clinician's decision-making on discontinuation of antibiotic treatment
- Pilot demonstrated that implementing PROCa™ correctly can help ↓ tracheitis treatment days
- In the future PCT can be used as an adjunct to support initiation of antibiotics for tracheitis and other clinical diagnoses